

Is it *right* if *left* out?

It was with surprise that I encountered some detailed insights into Costa and McCrae's study on the "Big Five" personality traits at Hagen University. The model introduced a taxonomy of stable personality traits, aiming to explain various facets of human behaviour, including emotional, interpersonal, and motivational tendencies (Costa & McCrae, 1995). However, what truly captured my attention were details regarding the intriguing connection between handedness and personality traits, particularly in view of adaptability and stress resilience (Lester, 1986). Left-handedness, typically regarded as a simple physical characteristic, has captivating links to both personality traits and increased stress susceptibility, with left-handedness, being overrepresented in some psychopathologies (Lester, 1986; Somers et al., 2009).

This notion left me reasoning for deeper questions about the nature of personality itself. Patterns of recurrent choices and actions sculpt our behavioural signatures, which in turn can shape our personality. If a reduced choice repertoire translates to a lower adaptability, ergo less stress-resilience, what could handedness suggest about the nature of how recurrent choices are made?

One scenario could be that handedness influences the processes involved in choice selections in such way that it increases susceptibilities to maladaptive behavioural patterns, shifting the odds towards diminished options to choose from. This leads to the core question of what neural mechanisms sustain the processing of multiple options, and how different choices are represented and sustained in the brain. Could handedness have a narrowing influence?

One likely candidate regulating choice-making and being related to altered handedness signatures of brain activity, is the dopaminergic system (Molochnikov & Cohen, 2014). Dopamine is crucial in modulating executive functions such as decision-making, learning, and goal-directed behaviours (Cools & D'Esposito, 2011). Interestingly, research has shown that dopaminergic activity is not uniformly distributed across the brain. Left-right hemispheric shifts in dopaminergic modulation differ ipsi & contralaterally regulating through opposite signatures different aspects of goal-oriented behaviours and choice selection (Hart et al., 2024). Dopamine release e.g. in the dorsal striatum, shows distinct lateralized activities playing a crucial role when integrating information about the relationship between actions and their outcomes, thus guiding the process of choice selection. In response to recurrent choices a lateralized dopamine signal aims towards integrating and encoding action-outcome relationships, thus invigorating behaviours (Hart et al., 2024). Strikingly, inputs to the dorsal striatum from the Substantia Nigra likewise show lateralized signature modulating the degree of movement vigor before actions are initiated. In this region, a subset of dopaminergic neurons specifically encodes before action initiation the length

of contralateral movement sequences, but not the ipsilateral ones (Mendonça et al., 2024).

If lateralized asymmetries in neural ensembles shape the signatures of choice sequences, how is one option chosen after another one from a set of possibilities and would there be a hierarchy of options? How is this information organized spatially and temporally within the brain, to be able to update information about multiple action algorithms to pick from?

Properties as handedness could shift intrinsic dopamine signatures towards higher odds for more rigid hierarchies, resulting in lower behavioural adaptability, thus intrinsically partly biasing action-outcome relationships. Disrupted Dopaminergic dynamics could affect the neural processes responsible for maintaining balances between different behavioural options, thus contributing to maladaptive behaviours.

The interplay between handedness, lateralization and dopamine activity could offer a fascinating window into the neural basis of choice selection. Behavioural rigidity might be shaped by the neurobiological mechanisms that define hierarchies of available options, and how their signatures are sustained or restricted over time. As we continue to unravel these complexities, the understanding of how factors like lateralization influences the dynamics of behavioural flexibility could offer new insights into neural mechanisms of choice selection. The nature of choice is driven by the possibility of selection itself, a necessity for every animal behaviour to be able to adapt to environmental demands. Lateralization could be an intrinsic principle contributing to the sustainability of option hierarchies, thus modulating their selection. While fundamental research can overlook at interhemispheric differences, it might be more worth to increasingly consider it regarding dopaminergic activity. Possibly dismissing lateralization as being marginally involved in selection dynamics, might be one choice to pick, but would it be *right* if *left* out?

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Image: Prompt "draw_a_stone_road_splitting_into_two_directions_symbolizing_choice_with_at_the_end_of_the_road_becoming_a_nervous_system," by Adobe, Adobe Firefly, 2024 (<https://firefly.adobe.com/>).